

Pulmonary Embolism with Large Thrombi in The Right Atrium While On Treatment with Anticoagulants-A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Pulmonary embolism (PE) is a severe cardiovascular syndrome, mostly caused by deep vein thrombosis (DVT), with high mortality, especially in elderly with multiple comorbidities. When thrombi in the right ventricle or atrium are present the prognosis is poorer. Here we present the case of a 78-year-old woman who suffered from an extended pulmonary embolism with large thrombi in the right atrium (RA), while receiving anticoagulant therapy.

Keywords: Pulmonary embolism; Cardiovascular syndrome; Old woman

INTRODUCTION

PE is one of the most common cardiovascular syndromes diagnosed in the Emergency Department (ED) and a major cause of cardiovascular mortality, especially in older patients with multiple comorbidities.[1] PE is mostly caused by DVT and some of the major predisposing factors are trauma, lower limb fracture, recent hospitalization and cancer.[2] Computed Tomographic Pulmonary Angiography (CTPA) is the gold standard method for the diagnosis of PE.[3] Assessment with bedside echocardiography is crucial, especially for hemodynamically unstable patients, for the evaluation of right ventricular pressure overload and dysfunction. The presence of thrombi in the right ventricle or atrium is rare and the prognosis is poorer. When thrombi are found in transthoracic echocardiography the diagnosis of PE is confirmed. [4]

CASE REPORT

A 79-year-old woman presented in the ED with chest pain and dyspnea gradually worsening the last two days. She also mentioned that ten days ago she injured her right leg after a fall. In her medical history she stated

chronic atrial fibrillation, for which she was receiving acenocumarol, arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus and dyslipidemia.

The clinical examination revealed hypoxia with oxygen saturation 88%, tachypnea, tachycardia (~120bpm) and normal blood pressure (120/80mmHg). The auscultation of lungs was normal, but in the ECG fast atrial fibrillation and S I, Q III, T III pattern were observed. A bed side transthoracic echocardiogram was performed in the ED which showed enlargement of the right ventricle (RV), RA and inferior vena cava (IVC) with concomitant signs of systolic dysfunction and pulmonary hypertension. In the RA, large oscillating formations were revealed, moving between RA and RV through the tricuspid valve, extended through the IVC. The clinical presentation, the ECG and the formations in the RA (thrombi) all led to the diagnosis of pulmonary embolism, which was confirmed by a CTPA, where emboli were found in the right main pulmonary artery, segmental and subsegmental branches.

Since she was hemodynamically stable, the patient was admitted in the intensive care unit and treatment with low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) was administered. International normalized ratio (INR) levels were borderline (~2). A low extremity vein ultrasound was performed and deep vein thrombosis in the right popliteal vein was found.

A few hours later, patient was clinically improved and oxygen saturation levels were restored. A second transthoracic echo was performed and surprisingly the large thrombi in the RA had already vanished.

Patient was stable, gradually improving during hospitalization, and discharged a few days later with a switch of the anticoagulation therapy from acenocumarol to apixaban.

DISCUSSION

PE is a severe cardiovascular syndrome, mostly caused by DVT. Mortality is high especially in elderly with multiple comorbidities. The presence of thrombi in the right cavities is not a common finding in hemodynamically stable patients with PE. Although patients with RA/RV thrombi have a worse clinical presentation, whether this finding affects the mortality is controversial.⁵ The current European Guidelines do not propose an alteration in the treatment or thrombolysis when thrombi in the right cavities are detected. [3] The current approach remains heparin or LMWH, except for cases with hemodynamic instability. What is curious with our case is that the PE and the large RA thrombi occurred while the patient was receiving therapeutic doses of acenocumarol. Even though anticoagulation with vitamin K antagonists (VKA) and direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) have similar effectiveness in patients with DVT and PE, difficulties in INR level regulation due to poor compliance, inadequate INR monitoring and multiple comorbidities make the choice of VKA less favourable. [5] In our patient, even though the INR levels were borderline, anticoagulation with VKA was inefficient. This is further supported by the fact that the patient was clinically improved and the thrombi vanished right after treatment with LMWH started. As a result, switch from VKA to DOACs was the preferred approach in order to achieve adequate anticoagulation.

CONCLUSION

PE is a severe cardiovascular syndrome and the presence of RV/RA thrombi is linked with worse clinical presentation. Heparin or LMWH is the proposed treatment for hemodynamically stable patients, and

thrombolysis is chosen only in cases with instability. In our case, where anticoagulation with VKA was inadequate, LMWH and a DOAC were considered the best choice for the treatment of a PE with large RA thrombi.

Images 1,2,3: Bedside transthoracic echocardiography, large thrombi moving between RA and RV through the tricuspid valve, extended through the IVC

Image 4: Computed Tomographic Pulmonary Angiography, emboli in the right main pulmonary artery.

Images 5,6: Second transthoracic echocardiography a few hours later, the thrombi have vanished

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